

NOTES

TABLE 2—IR AND ABSORPTION SPECTRAL DATA

Sl. No.	Complex	ν M—O I	ν M—O II	ν M—O III	Average β	Average δ	Average $b\frac{1}{2}$
1.	Pr(TFAA) ₃	412(ms)	375(m)	275(w)	0.9960	0.401	0.044
2.	Nd(TFAA) ₃	412(ms)	375(m)	277(w)	0.9956	0.467	0.047
3.	Sm(TFAA) ₃	414(m)	276(m)	277(w)	0.9949	0.512	0.050
4.	Ho(TFAA) ₃	415(m)	378(m)	277(w)	0.9917	0.836	0.064
5.	Er(TFAA) ₃	417(m)	380(m)	278(w)	0.9896	1.050	0.072
6.	Pr(HFAA) ₃	418(ms)	379(m)	280(w)	0.9938	0.623	0.055
7.	Nd(HFAA) ₃	420(ms)	383(m)	280(w)	0.9953	0.472	0.049
8.	Sm(HFAA) ₃	420(ms)	383(m)	281(w)	0.9946	0.543	0.052
9.	Ho(HFAA) ₃	420(ms)	384(m)	282(w)	0.9905	0.959	0.068
10.	Er(HFAA) ₃	423(ms)	385(m)	284(w)	0.9987	1.142	0.075
11.	Pr(BZTFA) ₃	416(ms)	377(m)	278(w)	0.9937	0.634	0.055
12.	Nd(BZTFA) ₃	416(ms)	378(m)	279(w)	0.9949	0.513	0.050
13.	Sm(BZTFA) ₃	418(ms)	380(m)	280(w)	0.9934	0.553	0.057
14.	Ho(BZTFA) ₃	419(ms)	382(m)	281(w)	0.9913	0.877	0.066
15.	Er(BZTFA) ₃	422(ms)	382(ms)	285(w)	0.9900	1.010	0.070
16.	Pr(PFBZA) ₃	422(ms)	378(m)	279(w)	0.9953	0.472	0.049
17.	Nd(PFBZA) ₃	422(m)	380(m)	282(w)	0.9936	0.644	0.056
18.	Sm(PFBZA) ₃	424(m)	380(m)	283(w)	0.9944	0.563	0.053
19.	Ho(PFBZA) ₃	426(m)	382(m)	285(w)	0.9898	1.080	0.073
20.	Er(PFBZA) ₃	428(m)	384(m)	287(w)	0.9873	1.286	0.080

of little significance, yet these values are useful in a comparative study of the bonding in these complexes.

These anhydrous complexes have been found to dissolve in organic solvents. The molar conductance of these chelates in benzene ranges between 3.2-5.8 mho and in DMF 10.0-12.0 mho suggesting that they behave almost like non-electrolyte. The low degree of dissociation suggests that these are of inner sphere complexes.

Acknowledgement

The author is grateful to Prof. R. C. Kapoor, Head of the Chemistry Department for his interest, suggestions and laboratory facilities. He also thanks Dr. Megh Singh, his student for valuable help in the present work.

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Polyamino Chelates of Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), Zn(II) and Pd(II) using Cysteine as a Secondary Ligand

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Manuscript received 19 August 1978, revised 21 April 1979, accepted 6 October 1979

A large number of studies on the interaction of transition metal ions with amino acids have been carried out because of their biological interest¹⁻⁵. They have also been studied in relation to the determination of their structure and formation constants using various physico-chemical methods. This information on the simple metal complexes of cysteine⁶⁻¹¹ are also available but a very little has been done on the mixed ligand complexes of this reagent¹²⁻¹⁴. The present investigation on ternary complexing system of bivalent metal ions involving dipyriddy and *o*-phenanthroline as primary and cysteine as secondary ligand, is an attempt to fill this gap.

Irving and Rossotti pH-titration technique¹⁵ as modified by Chidambaram and Bhattacharya¹⁶ has been used for the determination of stability constants. All the experiments were carried out at 24 ± 1° and at $\mu = 0.1M$ (NaClO₄) in aqueous

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medium. The titration curves for Ni(II)-dipy-cysteine system are given in Fig. 1. In other systems also, the nature of the curves were the same.

Solutions and related materials: All the solutions were prepared in doubly distilled CO₂ free water and the reagents used were of analytical grade. Solutions of metal chlorides (0.01M), perchloric acid (0.002M) and sodium perchlorate (1.0M) in double distilled water and of palladium chloride (0.01M) in 0.1M HCl were prepared and standardised. Solutions of the ligands were prepared by direct weighing.

Apparatus: As reported earlier¹⁷, electronic spectra were recorded using CZ-SPECORD-UV-VIS recording spectrophotometer.

Preparation of the complexes: The solutions (0.02M) of metal ion, amine (dipyridyl or phenanthroline) and cysteine were mixed in the ratio of 1 : 1 : 1 and then refluxed for half an hour on a water bath. The mixture was then allowed to cool in an ice bath for about 24 hr. The crystals formed were filtered, washed several times with 50% methanol to make the complexes free from reactants, dried in a desiccator over anhydrous sulfuric acid and then analysed for the metal, carbon and hydrogen.

[Co(C₁₀H₈N₂)(C₃H₅O₂NS)] –
Calcd. : Co, 17.64 ; C, 46.71 ; H, 3.89%.
Found : Co, 17.48 ; C, 46.24 ; H, 3.86%.

[Co(C₁₂H₈N₂)(C₃H₅O₂NS)] –
Calcd. : Co, 16.46 ; C, 50.28 ; H, 3.63%.
Found : Co, 16.31 ; C, 49.78 ; H, 3.59%.

[Ni(C₁₀H₈N₂)(C₃H₅O₂NS)] –
Calcd. : Ni, 17.59 ; C, 46.74 ; H, 3.89%.
Found : Ni, 17.50 ; C, 46.23 ; H, 3.84%.

[Ni(C₁₂H₈N₂)(C₃H₅O₂NS)] –
Calcd. : Ni, 16.41 ; C, 50.32 ; H, 3.63%.
Found : Ni, 16.31 ; C, 50.81 ; H, 3.60%.

[Cu(C₁₀H₈N₂)(C₃H₅O₂NS)] –
Calcd. : Cu, 18.77 ; C, 46.07 ; H, 3.83%.
Found : Cu, 18.67 ; C, 45.56 ; H, 3.80%.

[Cu(C₁₂H₈N₂)(C₃H₅O₂NS)] –
Calcd. : Cu, 17.52 ; C, 49.64 ; H, 3.58%.
Found : Cu, 17.44 ; C, 49.09 ; H, 3.53%.

[Zn(C₁₀H₈N₂)(C₃H₅O₂NS)] –
Calcd. : Zn, 19.20 ; C, 45.83 ; H, 3.81%.
Found : Zn, 19.05 ; C, 45.39 ; H, 3.79%.

[Zn(C₁₂H₈N₂)(C₃H₅O₂NS)] –
Calcd. : Zn, 17.94 ; C, 49.40 ; H, 3.56%.
Found : Zn, 17.76 ; C, 48.88 ; H, 3.53%.

[Pd(C₁₀H₈N₂)(C₃H₅O₂NS)] –
Calcd. : Pd, 27.89 ; C, 40.90 ; H, 3.40%.
Found : Pd, 27.62 ; C, 40.55 ; H, 3.38%.

[Pd(C₁₂H₈N₂)(C₃H₅O₂NS)] –
Calcd. : Pd, 26.24 ; C, 44.40 ; H, 3.20%.
Found : Pd, 25.92 ; C, 43.95 ; H, 3.16%.

All the complexes were non-electrolytic in 50% alcohol.

Results and Discussion

Titration curves for Ni-(DPY)-cys system are given in Fig. 1. Similar curves were obtained in the case of the other systems. 1 : 1 (Ni – DPY) complex is formed at pH ≈ 4.0 which remains stable up to pH ≈ 8.5 after which hydroxo complexes M(DPY)-(OH)_n are formed. Beyond pH ≈ 9.0, the complexes

Fig. 1. Curve A—25 ml HClO₄ (0.002M)
B—20 ml HClO₄ (0.002M) + 5 ml Cysteine (0.01M) in 0.002M HClO₄
C—Mixture A + 5 ml Dipyridyl (0.01M)
D—Mixture C + 5 ml Nickel Chloride (0.01M)
E—Mixture B + 5 ml Nickel Chloride (0.01M)
F—Mixture E + 5 ml Dipyridyl (0.01M)
Total volume made up = 60 ml ($\mu = 0.1$)

are decomposed to form the metal hydroxides which ultimately precipitate out. Mixed ligand titration curve departs from the curves of cysteine at a pH ≈ 5.5 i.e., above the formation of 1 : 1 (Ni – DPY) species and below the pH ≈ 8.5 at which the hydroxo complex is formed. Further, in the titration curve of Ni – DPY, the precipitates were formed at pH ≈ 9.2 while no precipitation was observed in the mixture F at this pH. This indicates that mixed ligand complexation has occurred. In the case of copper(II), a purple black colour appeared on mixing the solution of copper(II) and cysteine, faded and the solution then became turbid. This confirmed the observation of previous workers^{18,19} that copper(II) complexes of cysteine are highly unstable. But in presence of dipyridyl or *o*-phenanthroline such type of changes were not observed and the bluish green colour formed on

mixing the reactants remained stable during the course of the titration, and the formation of precipitates were observed only beyond $pH=9.4$.

The dissociation constants, pK_1 and pK_2 of cysteine at 24° were 8.05 and 10.30 respectively. These are in good agreement with the published values^{20,21}. The formation constants of the mixed ligand chelates are given in Table 1. The value of $\log K_{M-DPY}^{M-Phe}$ and $\log K_{M-DPY-Cys}^{M-Phe}$ of the metal complexes is less than the corresponding values for metal-cysteine ($\log K_1$) complexes because of statistical factors. In binary systems cysteine coordinates to the metal through amino and sulphhydryl group¹⁰ but in ternary systems as in our case, coordination seems to occur through amino and carboxylate ion as indicated by the lower values of stability constants. Such a lower value is also reported in the case of metal alanine complex ($\log K_1=5.94$) where also, the coordination occurs through amine and carboxylate ion².

TABLE 1—FORMATION CONSTANTS OF MIXED LIGAND CHELATES AT 24° ($\mu=0.1M$, $NaClO_4$)

Metal	$\log K_{M-DPY}^{M-Phe}$	$\log K_{M-DPY-Cys}^{M-Phe}$	$\log K_1^*$ (M-Cys)
Co(II)	4.45	4.30	9.30
Ni(II)	5.55	5.45	9.64
Cu(II)	6.00	5.90	Unstable
Zn(II)	5.35	5.05	9.86
Pd(II)	5.60	5.45	—

* Literature value.

The presence of a strong band at 3400 cm^{-1} and the shifting of a band from 1700 cm^{-1} (cysteine) to $\approx 1600\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (in complexes) in the ir spectra of complexes also indicated the coordination of the secondary ligand through amine and carboxylic group.

The electronic spectra of solutions of diamagnetic Ni(II) complexes in 50% ethanol gave five bands at 41000, 33500, 32500, 31000 and 26500 cm^{-1} corresponding to ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1E_g$, ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1A_{2g}$, ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1B_{1g}$, ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1B_{2g}$ and ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1A_{2g}$ transitions respectively. Similarly, the solutions of diamagnetic Pd(II) complexes gave the bands at 38000, 30000, 28500 and 22500 cm^{-1} corresponding to the ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1B_u$, ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1E_g$, ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1B_{1g}$ and ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1A_{2g}$ transitions respectively. The observed magnetic moment value 1.85 B.M. of Cu(II) complexes was very close to that predicted for spin only value. Three bands at 21500, 20000 and 16000 cm^{-1} were observed corresponding to the transitions, charge transfer, ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g$ and ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}$ respectively. Thus the complexes of Ni(II), Pd(II) and Cu(II) were found of square planer structure. In the case of Co(II) complexes, the value of magnetic moment was found to be 4.50 B.M. which is usually encountered in tetrahedral cobalt(II) complexes²². Secondly, their electronic spectra gave the bands at 25000 and 32500 cm^{-1} which correspond to ${}^4A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(F)$ and ${}^4A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ respectively.

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Infrared Spectra of Some New Dithiocarbamates

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Manuscript received 26 February 1981, revised 2 July 1981,
accepted 30 October 1981

THE present communication describes synthesis and infrared spectra of a new series of dithiocarbamates, $(C_6H_5CH_2)(R)NCS_2^-$, viz.,

$R=H$, benzylidithiocarbamate ($BzHNCS_2^-$),

$R=CH_3$, benzylmethyldithiocarbamate ($BzMeNCS_2^-$),

$R=C_2H_5$, benzylethyldithiocarbamate ($BzEtNCS_2^-$),

$R=C_3H_7$, benzylisopropyldithiocarbamate ($BziPrNCS_2^-$),

and $R=C_6H_5CH_2$, dibenzylidithiocarbamate ($Bz_2NCS_2^-$).

Variation in $\nu(CN)$ with the change in R group has been discussed. A comparison has also been